

Implementation and Effectiveness of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction Among High School Students in Tanjay City

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Abstract

Authentic assessment has become an essential approach in English instruction as it promotes real-world communication, critical thinking, and meaningful learning experiences. This study aimed to determine the extent of implementation and effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction among high school students in Tanjay City. Specifically, it examined the implementation of authentic assessment principles, compliance with assessment and grading standards, the perceived effectiveness of performance-based tasks, the use of English as a medium of instruction, and significant relationships and differences when grouped by students' profile variables. The study employed a descriptive, comparative, and correlational research design using a researcher-made survey questionnaire. The instrument was validated by 15 experts with a Content Validity Ratio (CVR) of 0.91, with all items meeting the minimum CVR requirement of 0.49, and a Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.91. The respondents were 352 students drawn from a population of 2,062 from eight high schools in the North District. Statistical tools used included frequency, percentage, weighted mean, mean ranks, standard deviation, Spearman's rho, Kruskal-Wallis, and Mann-Whitney U Test. Participation and increased engagement in collaborative, cooperative, performance-based tasks were the strongest indicators. In contrast, assessment accuracy obtained the lowest mean from the respondents. The results also revealed a significant and very strong positive relationship between the implementation of authentic assessment and its effectiveness in English instruction. Significant differences were found only for sex, with male students perceiving authentic assessment more positively than female students. The study's findings establish that authentic assessment practices are both consistently implemented and highly effective in English instruction. Despite the overall positive findings, the lower ratings in real-life task application, assessment accuracy, and gender difference indicate the need for continuous improvement in real-life task design, assessment accuracy, and gender-responsive strategies to strengthen further authentic assessment practices that support the learning needs of all students.

Keywords: *Authentic assessment, English instruction, performance-based assessment, assessment effectiveness, high school students*

Introduction

English reflects the nation's commitment to global competitiveness and access to academic and professional opportunities (Schmidt, 2019; Constantino-Archer, 2022). Evidence indicates persistent challenges in English proficiency among Filipino learners, with declines documented in standardized assessments and classroom performance (Dayag & Dita, 2017; Ocampo, 2021).

In connection, consistent implementation of performance-based and authentic assessments remains a challenge in many public schools. The impacts of performance-based assessment on student learning outcomes (Heydarnejad, Tagavipour, Patra, & Khafaga, 2022) explored how PBA affects reading comprehension, academic motivation, foreign language anxiety, and self-efficacy, supporting the impact of performance-based tasks on multiple student variables.

Re-Introducing Authentic Assessment in Classroom Assessment Courses (Papanastasiou, Giallousi, & Pitri, 2025) found that teachers' beliefs, skills, and intentions related to authentic assessment influence its implementation and feedback practices, and that teachers view authentic assessment positively despite implementation challenges.

In recognition of these challenges, the Department of Education (DepEd) has emphasized the adoption of more robust and learner-centered assessment practices. Through DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2020, the Department institutionalized the use of Performance-Based Tasks (PBTs) as a central strategy for assessing student learning outcomes (DepEd, 2020). Authentic assessment approaches, such as PBTs, require students to apply knowledge and skills in contextually meaningful, real-world tasks rather than relying solely on traditional paper-and-pencil tests (Taylor, 2021). Research demonstrates that authentic assessments can promote deeper learning, enhance student engagement, and provide richer evidence of higher-order thinking, communication, and real-world problem solving (Stiggins, 2017; Adjei, Opoku, & Boateng, 2023).

Moreover, while recent studies have explored assessment practices, many continue to focus primarily on teachers, with fewer studies highlighting student perspectives as a basis for improving instructional and assessment strategies (Reyes, 2021; Villanueva, L., & Abelito, J, 2025).

To address these gaps, this study aims to examine the relationships among compliance with DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2020, extent of use of English as the medium of instruction, implementation of authentic assessment principles, and perceived effectiveness of performance-based tasks in English instruction.

This study seeks to develop a teacher training design that supports sustainable, authentic assessment practices. By focusing on students' perspectives, this research provides a more grounded understanding of how assessment practices are experienced in actual classroom settings (Santos, 2020; Torres, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

The primary purpose of this study is to describe students' profile and their perceptions regarding the implementation and effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction, determine whether significant differences exist when grouped according to profile variables, and examine if there is a significant relationship between the perceived implementation and perceived effectiveness of authentic assessment.

Furthermore, the study aims to develop a teacher training design that supports sustainable authentic assessment practices in English instruction.

Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Type of School
 - d. Grade Level?
2. What is the extent of perceived implementation of authentic assessment in English instruction?
3. What is the extent of perceived effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of perceived implementation and perceived effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction?
5. Is there a significant difference in the extent of perceived implementation and perceived effectiveness when grouped according to students' profile variables?
6. Based on the findings, what teacher training design can be proposed to support sustainable, authentic assessment in English instruction?

Significance of the Study

This study will benefit the following stakeholders:

Students. As the primary participants, students will directly benefit from the study through improved learning experiences. By examining the extent of teachers' compliance with DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2020, the application of authentic assessment principles, and the use of English as the medium of instruction in performance-based tasks (PBTs), the study ensures that instructional strategies are more relevant, engaging, and effective. Consequently, students will have greater opportunities to participate in meaningful and authentic learning tasks that enhance their communicative competence, critical thinking, and ability to apply English in real-life situations.

Teachers. This study will provide teachers with valuable insights into how students perceive and respond to performance-based tasks, identifying which assessment activities are most effective and which present challenges. The findings will serve as a basis for developing instructional materials and designing teacher training programs that strengthen the application of authentic assessment principles, the use of English as the medium of instruction, and compliance with DepEd policies, thereby promoting the effective implementation of performance-based tasks.

School Administrators. The results of this study will assist school administrators in monitoring, supporting, and improving teachers' assessment practices in accordance with DepEd policies. The instructional materials and teacher training program developed from the findings may also serve as valuable resources for professional development, classroom supervision, instructional monitoring, and curriculum planning, particularly in promoting authentic performance-based assessment in English instruction.

Curriculum Developers. This study will identify practical challenges encountered in the implementation of performance-based tasks, including issues related to policy compliance, authentic assessment practices, and the use of English as the medium of instruction. These findings may serve as a basis for curriculum enhancement and the development of professional learning programs that support effective, feasible, and sustainable performance-based assessment in English classrooms.

Researcher. This study will deepen the researcher's understanding of authentic assessment and the implementation of performance-based tasks in English instruction. Conducting this research will further enhance the researcher's competencies in educational research, classroom assessment, and data analysis. Moreover, the findings will provide a basis for improving future instructional practices and assessment strategies, particularly in designing meaningful and effective performance-based tasks that are aligned with DepEd standards.

Future Researchers. This study contributes empirical data on students' experiences and perceived instructional outcomes related to PBTs. It presents a research model that combines quantitative and developmental approaches and can serve as a reference for future studies on performance-based assessment, student engagement, and language instruction.

Literature Review

Authentic assessment is grounded on the premise that students demonstrate learning most effectively when they perform meaningful tasks that reflect real-life situations. Wiggins (1990) argued that authentic assessment measures students' ability to apply acquired knowledge and skills through realistic performances rather than relying solely on traditional paper-and-pencil examinations. This approach emphasizes higher-order thinking, problem-solving, critical reflection, and the meaningful application of learning, making assessment an integral part of the instructional process.

Complementing this perspective, David Nunan (2004), through the principles of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), emphasized that language is best learned when learners actively engage in authentic communicative tasks with meaningful purposes. Rather than focusing exclusively on grammatical accuracy, TBLT encourages learners to use language in solving problems, exchanging information, completing projects, and participating in collaborative activities that resemble real-life communication. These theoretical foundations collectively support the implementation of authentic assessment in English instruction, where students develop communicative competence

through meaningful performance-based learning experiences. Likewise, Gulikers, Bastiaens, and Kirschner (2004) explained that authentic assessment should align learning objectives, instructional activities, and assessment tasks to ensure that students acquire knowledge and skills applicable beyond the classroom. Their framework highlights authenticity in task design, assessment criteria, learning context, and expected performance, reinforcing the importance of meaningful and learner-centered assessment.

Assessment and grading policies likewise play a significant role in ensuring the quality and consistency of authentic assessment implementation. In the Philippine educational system, Department of Education Order No. 31, s. 2020 establishes policy guidelines on classroom assessment, emphasizing that assessment should be valid, reliable, fair, inclusive, and supportive of learners' holistic development. The policy encourages teachers to employ varied assessment methods that measure learners' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values while providing opportunities for meaningful demonstration of learning. Similarly, the Department of Education (2015) stressed that classroom assessment should inform instruction and promote continuous learner improvement rather than merely assign grades.

Supporting these policies, Stiggins (2017) emphasized that effective classroom assessment enhances student motivation and achievement when teachers clearly communicate learning goals, assessment criteria, and constructive feedback. Taylor (2021) further explained that authentic assessment enables educators to evaluate students' abilities through real-world performances, allowing learners to demonstrate practical application of knowledge instead of isolated content recall. More recently, Papanastasiou, Giallousi, and Pitri (2025) reported that successful implementation of authentic assessment depends on teachers' assessment literacy, careful planning, and alignment between instructional objectives, learning activities, and assessment strategies. Collectively, these studies underscore the importance of assessment policies and instructional practices in ensuring effective implementation of authentic assessment in English classrooms.

Authentic assessment is commonly implemented through performance-based tasks that require learners to demonstrate communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking in realistic contexts. Numerous studies have reported the positive educational outcomes associated with these instructional approaches. Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) found that authentic assessment provides richer evidence of student learning than traditional examinations because it evaluates learners' ability to transfer knowledge and skills to meaningful situations. Likewise, Adjei, Opoku, and Boateng (2023) concluded that authentic assessment significantly improves learners' engagement, motivation, and academic performance by encouraging active participation in the learning process. Heydarnejad et al. (2022) similarly observed that performance-based assessment enhances students' higher-order thinking, communication skills, and collaborative learning while promoting learner autonomy.

Furthermore, Villarroel et al. (2020) emphasized that authentic assessment strengthens students' reflective thinking, self-regulation, and lifelong learning competencies because learners become actively involved in evaluating their own performance. These findings collectively suggest that authentic assessment and performance-based tasks contribute substantially to meaningful learning experiences and improved educational outcomes.

The effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction is further influenced by the consistent use of English as the medium of instruction and by learners' experiences during classroom implementation. Constantino-Archer (2022) emphasized that sustained exposure to English through classroom interaction improves learners' communicative competence, confidence, and language proficiency. Similarly, Dayag and Dita (2017) highlighted the importance of meaningful English language use in developing students' oral and written communication skills, while Erk and Pavičić Takač (2021) noted that language learning becomes more effective when learners actively use English in authentic communicative situations. Studies examining students' perceptions also support the effectiveness of authentic assessment. Bilal et al. (2022) reported that students generally perceive authentic assessment positively because it promotes active engagement, critical thinking, and meaningful participation.

Likewise, Salma and Prastikawati (2021) found that authentic assessment increases learners' confidence, motivation, and responsibility for their own learning. Recognizing the crucial role of teachers, Xu and Brown (2020) argued that assessment literacy and continuous professional development enable educators to design valid, reliable, and meaningful authentic assessments that effectively measure student learning.

Although previous studies consistently demonstrate the educational benefits of authentic assessment, relatively limited research has examined its implementation, effectiveness, compliance with assessment and grading policies, and use of English as the medium of instruction simultaneously among public high school students in the Philippine context. Addressing this gap, the present study investigated the implementation and perceived effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction among public high school students in the North District of the Schools Division of Tanjay City and examined the relationship between authentic assessment implementation and students' perceived effectiveness of performance-based tasks.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive, comparative, and correlational quantitative research design.

The descriptive design was utilized to determine and describe the students' profile variables, the extent of implementation of authentic assessment principles, and the perceived effectiveness of performance-based tasks, based on the responses of the student-respondents.

The comparative design was used to determine whether significant differences and relationships existed in the perceived implementation and effectiveness of authentic assessment when respondents were grouped according to profile variables such as age, sex, school, and grade level.

The correlational design was employed to examine the significant relationship between the extent of implementation of authentic assessment principles and the perceived effectiveness of performance-based tasks in English instruction.

Through these research designs, the study was able to evaluate the relationships and differences among the variables investigated, as well as examine the current practices and perceptions regarding the implementation and effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction.

The study made use of survey questionnaires with Likert scales to determine the extent of compliance with assessment and Grading, the extent of perceived Implementation of Authentic Assessment, the extent of perceived Effectiveness of Performance-Based Tasks, and the extent of English use as a medium of instruction.

Finally, the study adopted a developmental approach, wherein the researcher designed a Teacher-Training Program based on the least-implemented and least-effective authentic assessment performance-based tasks identified in the survey, thereby addressing authentic assessment, instructional needs, and sustainable implementation support.

This study was conducted in eight public high schools in the North District of the Schools Division of Tanjay City for the School Year 2025–2026. These schools offer Junior and Senior High School programs and implement authentic assessment practices in English instruction in accordance with Department of Education policies.

The participating schools were located in highland, midland, and lowland areas of the district. The inclusion of schools from these geographical settings provided a broader representation of students' perceptions regarding the implementation and effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction.

The total population of the study comprised 2,062 students from selected public high schools in the North District Division of Tanjay City. Using Slovin's Formula with a 5% margin of error ($e = 0.05$), the minimum required sample

size was computed. After determining the sample size, Stratified Proportional Random Sampling was employed to distribute the sample proportionately across the participating schools. Where n_h is the sample size for each school, N_h is the population of each school, N is the total population (2,062), and n is the total sample size (335).

Because proportional allocations yielded fractional values, the figures were rounded to whole numbers, resulting in a final allocated sample size of 337 respondents.

During the actual data collection, however, 352 valid responses were retrieved. Since this number exceeded the minimum required sample size and all responses met the inclusion criteria, all 352 valid responses were retained and utilized in the final data analysis to enhance representation and improve the reliability of the findings.

The respondents were selected based on the following criteria: currently enrolled students in public high schools within the North District Division of Tanjay City during the School Year 2025-2026; taking English as a subject, willing to participate voluntarily; present during the data collection period that can complete the survey questionnaire; and can understand and respond to the questionnaire, or requiring guided clarification when necessary.

This study utilized a self-made survey questionnaire checklist in gathering the data with a set of structured items. The questionnaire consisted of a five-point Likert scale ranging from Never, Rarely, Sometimes, Often, and Always, with corresponding numerical values from 1 to 5, respectively, for statistical interpretation.

The instrument was adapted from established studies and relevant literature on authentic assessment and performance-based learning, and was subjected to content validation by experts to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research objectives.

It consists of five (5) parts, namely: Student profile in terms of age, sex, school, and grade level; The Extent of Compliance with Assessment and Grading (DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2020); The Extent of Implementation of Authentic Assessment Principles; The Extent of Perceived Effectiveness of Performance-Based Tasks; and Extent of Use of English as Medium of Instruction in Performance-Based Tasks.

The researcher sent a letter of request to the Schools Division Superintendent. After the request was approved with an endorsement letter from the Superintendent, a pilot test was conducted, and then the questionnaires were distributed to all eight (8) High Schools of the North District. Two weeks later, the questionnaires were retrieved, tallied, tabulated, and computed.

The Content Validity Ratio (CVR) was computed using the following formula:

$$CVR = \frac{n_e - \frac{N}{2}}{\frac{N}{2}}$$

Where n_e is the number of experts who rated the item as essential and N is total number of experts. For this study, N is the 15 validators. All 34 items obtained CVR values exceeding the minimum acceptable CVR of 0.49 across a panel of 15 validators, yielding an overall Content Validity Index (CVI) of 0.910.

The detailed item-by-item CVR computations are presented in Appendix C.

These validators are composed of individuals holding master's degrees in Education with specializations in English Language Teaching, English and Literature, and Administration and Supervision, as well as doctoral degrees in Educational Management and Applied Linguistics. They are experienced educators currently serving as teachers, school administrators, and college instructors in various education institutions.

Results of the validation showed that all items obtained CVR values meeting or exceeding the required threshold, indicating that the items were considered essential by the majority of the validators. This implies that the instrument has acceptable content validity and is appropriate for measuring the variables of the study.

For reliability, a pilot test was conducted, and the instrument was analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha. The overall reliability coefficient obtained was 0.91, which indicates excellent internal consistency.

Specifically, items 1–8 yielded $\alpha = 0.85$ (very good), items 9–18 yielded $\alpha = 0.76$ (acceptable to good), items 19–26 yielded $\alpha = 0.83$ (good), and items 27–34 yielded $\alpha = 0.97$ (excellent internal consistency). Items with relatively lower reliability were improved to achieve consistency.

Overall, the validity and reliability tests confirm that the research instrument is both valid and reliable, making it suitable for data collection.

Results

Problem Number 1 sought to determine the profile of the participants when grouped according to Age, Sex, School, and Grade Level.

Table 1.1 shows a summary of the participants' ages when grouped according to age brackets. Data shows that 17.33% are ages 18 and above, 46.88% are ages 16-17, and 35.80% are ages 13-15.

Table 1.2 shows the profile of participants when grouped by sex. Data shows that 36.40% of the participants are Male while 63.60% are Female. This shows that majority of the participants are female.

Table 1.3 shows the profile of participants when grouped according to School shows that there are 20 or 5.70% participants from School 2, both 32 or 9.10% from School 1 and School 7, 33 or 9.40% from School 6, 37 or 10.50% from School 4, 40 or 11.40% from School 5, 53 or 15.10% from School 3, 105 or 29.80% from School 8.

Table 1.4 shows the profile of participants when grouped according to Grade Level shows that there are 89 or (25.3%) participants who are Grade 9; 93 or (26.4%) who are Grade 10, 83 or (23.6%) who are Grade 11; and 87 or (24.7%) who are Grade 12.

Problem 2 sought to determine the extent of perceived implementation of authentic assessment principles in English instruction. Table 2 shows the Extent of Implementation of Authentic Assessment Principles. Table 2 indicates item number 7 "I participate in collaborative and interactive activities when doing performance-based tasks such as group projects, peer discussions, and cooperative presentations," obtained the highest mean of 4.34 indicating that respondents reported the highest participation in collaborative and interactive activities in Performance-Based Tasks.

Table 2.1 shows the Extent of Compliance with Assessment and Grading in English Instruction. Table 2.1 indicates item number 3 "The teacher clearly explains the instructions and expectations when giving performance-based tasks, such as real-life simulations, applied language tasks, and contextualized activities," obtained the highest mean of 4.58 indicating that respondents perceived that their teacher in English Very Highly complies clear explanations on the instructions and expectations in giving performance-based tasks.

Problem 3 sought to determine the extent of perceived effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction. Table 3 shows the Extent of perceived effectiveness of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction. Table 3 indicates item number 4 "Performance-based tasks increase my engagement and participation such as joining class discussions, participating in group activities, and completing interactive tasks," obtained the highest mean of 4.37

indicating that respondents perceived that Performance-based Tasks best effective in the increase of their engagement and participation.

Table 3.1 shows the Extent of Use of English as a medium of Instruction in Performance-Based Tasks in English Instruction. Table 3.1 indicates item number 1 “My teacher gives instructions for performance-based tasks in the English language, for example, explaining what to do in a project, presentation, or role play,” obtained the highest mean of 4.71 indicating that respondents perceived that their teacher in English consistently used the English language when giving instructions on performance-based tasks.

This is followed by item number 3, “My teacher communicates in the English language during class discussions, for example, asking questions, giving ideas, or explaining answers.,” with a mean score of 4.58. The composite mean of 4.48, interpreting English is consistently used as the medium of instruction in all aspects of performance-based tasks.

Problem 4 sought to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the Implementation and the Effectiveness of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction. Using Spearman Correlation Coefficient (ρ), with a p-value of 0.000001, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the results indicate that there is a significant relationship between the Implementation and Effectiveness of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction. The hypothesis, therefore, is rejected.

The results revealed a significant and very strong positive relationship between the implementation of authentic assessment and its effectiveness in English instruction. The findings indicate a positive association between high perceived implementation of authentic assessment with high perceived effectiveness. This finding is supported by recent studies which show that well-implemented authentic assessment enhances student learning outcomes and 21st-century skills such as critical thinking and communication (Adjei, Opoku, & Boateng, 2023). Similarly, research by Villarroel et al. (2020) emphasized that alignment between assessment tasks and real-world applications significantly increases the effectiveness of assessment practices.

Problem 5.1 sought to determine if there is a significant difference between the implementation of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction when grouped according to Students’ Profile variables in terms of Age, Sex, School, and Grade Level. The table presents differences in responses by students’ profile variables, using the Kruskal-Wallis Test and Mann-Whitney U Test at the 0.05 level of significance.

The results show that students aged 18 years old and above obtained the highest mean rank (180.5), followed by those aged 13–15 years old (177.1), while respondents aged 16–17 years old had the lowest mean rank (174.6). The computed value ($H = 0.16$) with a p-value of 0.9231 is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This indicates that age did not significantly influence the respondents' scores.

In terms of sex, male students recorded a higher mean rank (205.8) compared to female students (159.8). The computed value ($U = 10586$) with a p-value of less than 0.0001, is less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0). This means that there is a statistically significant difference between male and female respondents. Hence, sex significantly influences the responses.

Among the schools, Midland School obtained the highest mean rank (181.4), followed by Highland School (175.7) and Lowland School (172.4). However, the computed value ($H = 0.44$) and p-value (0.8025) indicate that the result is not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected, suggesting that school affiliation does not significantly affect the responses.

For grade levels, Grade 9 students obtained the highest mean rank of 190.6, followed by Grade 12 (178.7), Grade 11 (170.2), and Grade 10 (166.6). Despite these variations, the computed value ($H = 2.95$) with a p-value of 0.3994 is

greater than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating that there is no significant difference in responses across grade levels.

Problem 5.2 sought to determine if there is a significant difference between the Effectiveness of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction when grouped according to Students' Profile variables in terms of Age, Sex, School, and Grade Level. The table presents the differences in respondents' scores when grouped by profile variables, using the Kruskal-Wallis Test and Mann-Whitney U Test at a 0.05 level of significance.

In terms of age, respondents aged 13–15 obtained the highest mean rank (180.7), followed by those aged 16–17 (176) and 18 and above (169.2). However, the computed value ($H = 0.54$) with a p-value of 0.7634 exceeds the 0.05 significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating that there is no significant difference in responses when grouped according to age.

For sex, male respondents obtained a higher mean rank (196.8) compared to female respondents (164.9). The computed value ($U = 11735$) and p-value (0.0047) are less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that a significant difference exists between male and female respondents, suggesting that sex influences the measured variable.

When grouped according to school, Midland School recorded the highest mean rank (180.0), followed by Highland School (175.7) and Lowland School (173.9). Despite these differences, the computed value ($H = 0.21$) and p-value (0.9003) are greater than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating that there is no significant difference in responses across schools.

In terms of grade level, Grade 9 students obtained the highest mean rank (183.7), followed by Grade 10 (178.5), Grade 12 (178.4), and Grade 11 (164.6). However, the computed value ($H = 1.64$) with a p-value of 0.6504 exceeds the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating that grade level does not significantly affect the responses.

Discussion

Table 1 sought to determine the profile of the participants when grouped according to Age, Sex, School, and Grade Level. Table 1.1 shows 46.88% or near half of the respondents are from the ages of 16-17. Table 1.2 shows majority of the respondents are female or 63.60% Table 1.3 data shows 38.92% respondents come from lowland schools, and Table 1.4 shows grade levels 9-12 were relatively balanced ranging from 23 to 26%.

Table 2 sought to determine the extent of perceived implementation of authentic assessment principles in English instruction. The composite mean of 4.16, interpreting Authentic Assessment principles are frequently applied in most tasks. This result suggests that authentic and performance-based assessments may enhance student engagement and learning outcomes (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). These findings also support the study of Wiggins (1998), which emphasized that authentic assessment is effectively implemented when learners are engaged in real-world and meaningful tasks. Similarly, Gulikers et al. (2004) highlighted that alignment between learning tasks and real-life applications strengthens the implementation of authentic assessment practices.

Table 2.1 shows the Extent of Compliance with Assessment and Grading in English Instruction. Angulo (2023) emphasized that delivering well-structured instructions is as important as the teaching content itself. Clear and specific prompts directly guide students' performance and minimize ambiguity, which may otherwise lead to frustration or failure in completing classroom activities. This is followed by item number 4, "The teacher makes sure that the tasks assess both our knowledge and practical skills such as explaining concepts, applying skills in tasks, and solving real-life problems using English.," with a mean score of 4.50. The composite mean of 4.43, interpreting Assessment and grading practices are consistently aligned with standards in performance-based tasks.

Table 3 sought to determine the extent of perceived effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction. Respondents perceived that Performance-based Tasks best effective in the increase of their engagement and participation. According to Wang (2025), structured active-learning environments strongly promote communication and shared responsibility among peers. The study further revealed that active and task-centered learning approaches lead to higher levels of classroom participation and satisfaction with interaction compared to lecture-centered methods. This is followed by item number 1, “Performance-based tasks require me to perform real-world communication tasks such as giving speeches, joining group discussions, and writing letters or emails,” with a mean score of 4.32.

In contrast, item number 7 “Performance-based tasks allow accurate assessment of my language performance”, obtained the lowest mean of 4.14. This indicates that students generally perceive performance-based tasks as useful in evaluating their language abilities; however, some respondents expressed uncertainty regarding the consistency and accuracy of assessment outcomes. The composite means of 4.25, interpreting Performance-based tasks are highly effective, greatly improving students’ skills, engagement, and learning.

This result is consistent with the findings of Luan and Narayanan (2024), who reported that authentic assessment significantly enhances student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes in technology-based and performance-oriented learning environments. Moreover, Adjei, Opoku, and Boateng (2023) found that performance-based tasks significantly improve students’ critical thinking and communication skills.

Table 3.1 shows the Extent of Use of English as a medium of Instruction in Performance-Based Tasks in English Instruction. Respondents perceived that their teacher in English consistently used the English language when giving instructions on performance-based tasks and that English is consistently used as the medium of instruction in all aspects of performance-based tasks.

Erk and Pavičić Takač (2021) found that students exposed to classrooms dominated by teacher target-language input demonstrated a significant long-term advantage in aural comprehension compared to those exposed to code-switching environments. The study further suggested that sustained target-language exposure contributes to learners’ situational confidence and overall language acquisition.

Table 4 sought to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the Implementation and the Effectiveness of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction. The results indicate that there is a significant relationship between the Implementation and Effectiveness of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction. The hypothesis, therefore, is rejected.

The results revealed a significant and very strong positive relationship between the implementation of authentic assessment and its effectiveness in English instruction. The findings indicate a positive association between high perceived implementation of authentic assessment with high perceived effectiveness. This finding is supported by recent studies which show that well-implemented authentic assessment enhances student learning outcomes and 21st-century skills such as critical thinking and communication (Adjei, Opoku, & Boateng, 2023). Similarly, research by Villarroel et al. (2020) emphasized that alignment between assessment tasks and real-world applications significantly increases the effectiveness of assessment practices.

Table 5.1 sought to determine if there is a significant difference between the implementation of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction when grouped according to Students’ Profile variables in terms of Age, Sex, School, and Grade Level. The findings reveal that only sex shows a significant difference in the responses, while age, school, and grade level do not significantly influence the results. This suggests that the measured variable is generally consistent across most demographic groups, except when respondents are grouped according to sex. Sudewi and Widhi (2025) reported that gender-based differences influence students’ engagement in English language instruction. Their study found that male students tend to prefer verbal, interactive, and real-world communication

activities and often exhibit greater confidence during active classroom participation. In contrast, female students were observed to favor more structured and written forms of expression.

Table 5.2 sought to determine if there is a significant difference between the Effectiveness of Authentic Assessment in English Instruction when grouped according to Students' Profile variables in terms of Age, Sex, School, and Grade Level.

Overall, the results show that only sex has a significant effect on responses, whereas age, school, and grade level do not. This implies that the observed variations across most profile variables are not statistically meaningful, except for sex. Saaty (2022) emphasized that motivation and gender are influential factors in English language learning, noting that learners of different sexes exhibit varying perspectives and responses toward the language-learning process.

The study revealed that female participants demonstrated higher motivation in learning English, suggesting that sex-related differences may influence students' engagement, participation, and learning preferences in English instruction. These findings indicate that male and female learners may differ in how they perceive and respond to instructional approaches and classroom activities. This finding contrasts with the results of the present study, wherein male respondents obtained significantly higher scores in the effectiveness of authentic assessment in English instruction compared to female respondents. The significant difference by sex suggests that male and female students may respond differently to authentic assessment strategies, particularly those involving performance-based, interactive, and practical learning activities. The result further implies that sex may play a role in shaping students' perceptions and experiences regarding the effectiveness of authentic assessment in the English classroom.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the perceived implementation of authentic assessment in English instruction is frequently practiced, as reflected by the overall composite mean. There is a strong perceived compliance with assessment and grading standards, particularly in aligning tasks with learning competencies and communicating expectations.

Consequently, performance-based tasks are perceived as highly effective particularly in enhancing students' engagement and higher-order thinking skills. Among the indicators, student participation in collaborative activities received the highest rating, indicating that authentic assessment in groups and pairs promote interaction.

However, assessment tasks that require students to apply English in real-life situations obtained the lowest rating, suggesting an area for improvement in connecting classroom learning to real-world contexts.

Moreover, the study revealed a very strong and statistically significant relationship between the implementation and perceived effectiveness of authentic assessment, indicating that respondents who perceived higher levels of implementation also tended to report higher perceived learning outcomes.

In contrast, the accuracy of assessment received the lowest rating, implying a need to further strengthen assessment practices to ensure that student performance is measured more precisely and consistently. The results also show that students' perceptions are generally consistent across age, school type, and grade level, suggesting uniformity in instructional practices regardless of geographical location and school size.

However, significant differences by sex imply that male and female students may experience or perceive authentic assessment differently. As the present study did not investigate the underlying factors contributing to this variation, further research is recommended to examine the mechanisms and contextual influences that may account for these differences.

Despite the overall positive findings, certain areas require improvement. These include the need to strengthen the use of English in real-life contexts, the quality and consistency of assessment feedback, and the use of performance-based learning experiences.

Therefore, while authentic assessment practices are effective and consistently implemented, targeted enhancements are necessary to ensure a more inclusive, responsive, and optimized learning experience for all students.

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

Teachers should design more tasks that simulate real-world communication such as interviews, workplace scenarios, and community-based activities.

Teachers should improve the accuracy of assessment practices by refining evaluation methods, ensuring that performance-based tasks more precisely measure students' performance.

Teachers should adopt inclusive and responsive teaching strategies to address differences in perceptions between male and female students regarding implementation and effectiveness. Further research may be conducted to better understand the factors contributing to these variations and inform appropriate instructional interventions.

Schools should continue strengthening the implementation of authentic assessment, as it has been shown to significantly influence its effectiveness.

Schools should conduct teacher training programs as professional development to focus on improving weak areas identified in the study such as assessment tasks involving real-life situations, accuracy of assessment, and gender-responsive authentic assessment and performance-based tasks.

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